

Diffuse wave-field correlation in space: An instantaneous time-reversal mirror for Green's function retrieval of dense arrays

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Abstract

We show theoretically that diffuse wave-field cross-correlations in space between two times are equivalent to the focusing field created by an instantaneous time-reversal mirror. The cross-correlations in space thus allow retrieving the medium’s Green’s function between two discrete times. Our demonstration completes the existing theoretical framework on Green’s function retrieval by formally establishing a link between cross-correlations in space and volumetric time-reversal. This link is put into context with the spatial autocorrelation (SPAC), boundary time-reversal, and time-domain noise correlation methods. We illustrate the instantaneous and volumetric time-reversal focusing via diffuse wave-field correlations in a linear elastic numerical experiment. This experiment showcases how to leverage cross-correlations in space for near instantaneous medium property monitoring with dense arrays.

Historically, diffuse wave fields have been considered as noise, that deteriorates signal quality, and thus poses issues in imaging applications. However, during the last decades, acoustic and elastic noise correlation imaging has emerged as an alternative to imaging with coherent wavefronts, and has found a broad range of applications that spans from seismology to medical imaging and non-destructive testing. The method is rooted in the principle of seismic interferometry, which, put simply, creates a new seismic signal from the correlation of the seismic signals at two receivers [1, 2]. Claerbout’s pioneering work in the 1960s [3] was followed by independent work in acoustics [4] and later on by developments in seismic imaging [5], helioseismology [6], ultrasound [7], earthquake seismology [8], ocean acoustics [9], non-destructive testing [10], [11], medical imaging, electromagnetic diffusion and electrokinetic waves [12]. In summary, for uncorrelated noise sources, the cross-correlation in time between the signals recorded at two receiver positions yields the Green’s function between them. For the elastodynamic case, this has been shown by [13], based on a correlation-type reciprocity theorem (in time).

In parallel, advances in acoustics led to the development of the Time Reversal Mirror (TRM), which allows focusing of a wave-field through a scattering medium via boundary control [14–19]. Both concepts, the TRM and seismic interferometry, are closely linked [20–24] [25], and have led to an impressive range of theoretical insights and practical imaging applications over the last thirty years.

While seismic noise interferometry is performed on time-domain signals, the seismology community has been using a related frequency domain method, the spatial auto-correlation (SPAC) method [26], since Aki proposed it in 1957 [27]. SPAC usually employs averages over time for ensemble averaging. The fundamental consistency of interferometry and SPAC has been outlined by [28, 29]. [30] established that the Green’s function can be retrieved from the (temporal) integral of the normalized spatial correlation of a random scalar field. However, cross-correlation of spatial signals (space-series instead of time-series) of dense arrays at different instants in time (time states) were until recently a non-existing field in acoustic and elastic ambient noise applications. SPAC applications for example rely mostly on integrating a measured time-series. Recently, [31] derived the retrieval of the temporal Green’s function for time-dependent media through spatial correlations. Here, spatial correlations signify the cross-correlation in the spatial domain between time state A and time state B (equation 57 in [31]). In contrast to Green’s function retrieval between space states, this results in a single-sided representation. Single-sided here signifies that

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Figure 1: Sketch illustrating the context of this paper with respect to different concepts based on reciprocity and time-reversal invariance: Boundary time-reversal, Green’s function retrieval through wave-field correlation over time and SPAC have been linked previously by the indicated publications. The present manuscript establishes the link of correlations in space with the volumetric time-reversal through the instantaneous time mirror.

sources only fire at times prior to the time states which enter the correlation, a condition imposed by causality. In comparison, space-dependent Green’s function retrieval requires sources surrounding the receivers.

The concept of the time-reversal mirror (TRM) has recently been extended to the volumetric or Instantaneous Time-reversal Mirror (ITM). In a beautiful experiment, [32] show that an instantaneous modulation of the medium properties in the form of a Delta-like pulse leads to volumetric time-reversal of any propagating wave-field inside that medium. They further establish an equivalence of this modulation with the imposition of new initial conditions through the introduction of volumetric secondary Huygens sources. With respect to this experiment, [33, 34] noted that the time-reversal of a diffuse wave-field can be recovered perfectly for cross-correlations of very small time windows, given sufficient volumetric sources.

In the present work, we will formally establish the link between the Instantaneous Time Mirror and Green’s function retrieval of diffuse wave-fields. We show theoretically that cross-correlations in space between two time states are equivalent to performing a volumetric or instantaneous time-reversal. This equivalence establishes a missing link in the related concepts of TRM, ITM, SPAC and interferometry, which is sketched in Fig. 1. We then illustrate the established link through a numerical experiment. Through this linear elastic numerical experiment, we show how cross-correlations in space of two time states of a field due to random noise sources inside a medium of interest can be used for near instantaneous monitoring of the medium’s wave speed.

SPATIAL CROSS-CORRELATION AND THE ITM - THEORY

In this section, we first review the well-known equivalence of a boundary time-reversal experiment with numerical cross-correlation in time. We then describe the action of an Instantaneous Time-reversal Mirror (ITM) on the wave-field created by a Dirac Delta source via Green's functions. We establish the ITM's equivalence with numerical cross-correlations in space between two time states of the wave-field created by a Dirac Delta source. Furthermore, we show that this equivalence still holds for the correlation in space of a spatially diffuse wave-field for (1) the case of temporally correlated and (2) the case of temporally uncorrelated distributed noise sources. Lastly, we demonstrate that our results are a generalisation of the SPAC method, as applied in seismology, thus closing the loop in Fig. 1. Throughout the theoretical part of the manuscript, we will use G for Green's functions that map space-time states to space-time states, G_r for Green's functions that map space states to space states for all times t , and G_t for Green's functions that map time states to time states for the entire space \mathbf{r} . By definition, G_r assumes time-invariance and G_t assumes space-invariance. However, in order to close the loop in Fig. 1, it is sufficient to assume a space- and time-invariant medium for the whole present manuscript.

Before formally establishing the ITM - cross-correlation analogy, let us restate the well-known equivalence of a boundary time-reversal experiment with the cross-correlation of a diffuse wave-field in time through Green's functions [20–22, 24, 36, 38]:

Boundary time-reversal

Following [22, 24], the time-reversal experiment can be stated as follows: an impulsive source $\delta(\mathbf{r}-\mathbf{r}_A, t-t_s)$ (Dirac Delta) at a position $\mathbf{r}_A \in V$ inside the enclosing boundary ∂V at the source excitation time $t_s = 0$ creates a wave-field. Its signal is registered, time-reversed and re-emitted into the medium on the surface $\mathbf{r}' \in \partial V$. Due to time-reversal invariance, this re-emitted field is described by the same wave equation as the initial field. The resulting wave-field ϕ at any receiver location $\mathbf{r} \in V$ inside the medium is then:

$$\phi(\mathbf{r}, t) \propto \int_{\partial V} G_r(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}', t) *_t G_r(\mathbf{r}', \mathbf{r}_A, -t) d\mathbf{r}', \quad (1)$$

where G_r is the Green's function for a temporally homogeneous (time invariant) medium and $*_t$ is the (temporal) convolution operator. We chose \mathbf{r} to indicate that G_r maps space states (positions) to space states for all times t . This wave-field resulting from the re-emission at the boundary focuses in \mathbf{r}_A at focal time t_A , from where it then diverges for $t > t_A$. We can now interpret the resulting wavefield ϕ for $t < t_A$ as the acausal (ingoing and focusing) field and for $t > t_A$ as the causal (outgoing and diverging) field due to a source at t_A, \mathbf{r}_A , with $t_A = 0$:

$$\phi(\mathbf{r}, t) = G_r(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}_A, t) + G_r(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}_A, -t) \quad (2)$$

Combining Eq. (1) and Eq. (2), exploiting source receiver reciprocity, and choosing one receiver by setting $\mathbf{r} = \mathbf{r}_B$, we observe the following:

$$G_r(\mathbf{r}_B, \mathbf{r}_A, t) + G_r(\mathbf{r}_B, \mathbf{r}_A, -t) \propto \int_{\partial V} G_r(\mathbf{r}_B, \mathbf{r}', t) *_t G_r(\mathbf{r}_A, \mathbf{r}', -t) d\mathbf{r}' \quad (3)$$

The convolution of the signals of one receiver at \mathbf{r}_B with the time-reversed signal at receiver \mathbf{r}_B due to the sources on \mathbf{r}' leads to the retrieval of an approximation of the acausal Green's function $G_r(\mathbf{r}_B, \mathbf{r}_A, -t)$, and causal Green's function $G_r(\mathbf{r}_B, \mathbf{r}_A, t)$. Hence, the cross-correlation (a convolution with a time-reversed signal) of the signals in \mathbf{r}_A and \mathbf{r}_B leads to an approximation of the impulse response and its time-reverse in \mathbf{r}_B for a source at \mathbf{r}_A . We skip the derivation of the well established extension for noise sources. It can be shown that the cross-correlation in time between one receiver (space state) and all others of a diffuse wave-field results in a time-reversal (ingoing and focusing) field for negative lag times and a diverging outgoing field for positive lag times. The Time-Reversal-Mirror is schematically illustrated in Fig. 2(a). The correlation of a diffuse wave-field due to distributed noise sources is sketched in Fig. 2(b). Correlation of the field at \mathbf{r}_A with that at all \mathbf{r} of (b) results in the TR-field in (a). To obtain the exact Green's function, a complete representation containing G_r and its time derivative is required instead of the simplified equation 3 [2]. This can be seen as simultaneously capturing the monopole and dipole response. However, in the case of a sufficiently large closed boundary or perfect time-reversal device [2], the dipole component can be approximated by $-i\frac{\omega}{c}$ times the monopole component. In the time domain this component can be approximated by $\frac{1}{c}\partial_t G_r(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}', t)$ [39]. Hence, the proportionality sign in Eq. (3), which in practice is often sufficient.

Volumetric time-reversal

We will now perform a similar thought experiment for cross-correlations in space and the ITM. Let us therefore introduce volumetric time reversal by an ITM: Consider an impulsive source $\delta(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}_0, t - t_S)$, that emits a signal at \mathbf{r}_0, t_S . At $t_{ITM} > t_S$, Losschmidt's daemon flips the momentum polarity of each particle everywhere in the volume [40]. Thus, $\lim_{t \rightarrow t_{ITM}^-} \phi(t) = \lim_{t \rightarrow t_{ITM}^+} \phi(t)$, but $\lim_{t \rightarrow t_{ITM}^-} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \phi(t) = -\lim_{t \rightarrow t_{ITM}^+} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \phi(t)$. Due to time-reversal invariance, the wave will exactly backtrace its path to the origin and the wave vector \mathbf{k} is flipped. While this might appear as a purely theoretical thought experiment, the same time-reversed wave can be reached through a Losschmidt freezing. There, the field is frozen for a moment in time ($\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \phi(t) = 0$) and instantaneously 'melted' again ($\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \phi(t) \neq 0$). In the moment of total freeze, the particles lose memory of their directionality (velocity). The frozen amplitude (pressure or displacement) acts as a Huygens' source when melted, and thus creates forward and backward propagation [41].

The field will split into a transmission and a reflection at $t > t_{ITM}$. The reflection is a spatially reversed version of the incident field ϕ^{Inc} , which exists at times $t < t_{ITM}$. Since the reflection backtraces the path of the incident field, it is often called a time-reversed field in the literature. Hence, for any dt with $t_{ITM} - dt > t_S$, the time-reflected field $\phi^{ITM_r}(t_{ITM} + dt, \mathbf{r}) = \frac{1}{2}\phi^{Inc}(t_{ITM} - dt, \mathbf{r})$ exists. This time-reversal effect can also be achieved by any decoupling of the evolution or time-derivative of the field from the field itself. This has been experimentally shown by [32, 42] and has been named the Instantaneous Time Reversal Mirror. The strength of the medium modulation which decouples the field and its derivative will define the Amplitude ratios of incident, transmitted and reflected fields, where the maximum reflection coefficient is limited to 0.5 [31, 43, 44] in the case of 'Losschmidt freezing'. For a perfect delta modification, the transmission is simply the continuation of the incident field with a modified amplitude.

Let us now describe the action of an Instantaneous time mirror using Green's functions. For clarity, we will start with the general Green's function G , that maps a space-time state to

Figure 2: Illustration of cross-correlations in time and space and their Time-Reversal equivalents. Space-time limits of diffuse wave-fields entering the correlations are indicated by cylinders. Stars represent Dirac Delta sources, located at the vertex of the corresponding wave-fields represented by space-time cones. Small circles represent active (black) and passive (gray) volumetric and boundary sources: TR sources in (a),(c) and distributed noise sources in (b),(d). $x - y$ planes indicate snapshots in time (time states), with $t_B^{+/-} = t_A \pm \Delta t$. A space-time slice of the diffuse wavefield entering a correlation in time is shown in (b) and corresponding 2D space slices entering a correlation in space are shown in (d). (a) TRM located in \mathbf{r}' acting on a delta source at t_S, \mathbf{r}_A . TR-equivalent to CC^t , shown in b). (b) Cross-correlation of temporal signals CC^t . Signals in different locations are shifted in time. (c) ITM at t_{ITM} of a delta source at t_S, \mathbf{r}_A - TR-equivalent to CC^r , shown in d). (d) Cross-correlation of spatial signals CC^r . Signals in different snapshots are shifted in space.

another space-time state. The field due to volume (distributed) sources $\delta(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}', t - t_{ITM})$ at $\mathbf{r}' \in V$ and t_{ITM} following a space-time delta excitation $\delta(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}_0, t - t_S)$ at t_S, \mathbf{r}_0 is described by:

$$\phi^{ITM}(t_B, \mathbf{r}) \propto \int_V G(t_B, \mathbf{r} | t_{ITM}, \mathbf{r}') G(t_{ITM}, \mathbf{r}' | t_S, \mathbf{r}_0) d\mathbf{r}', \quad \mathbf{r} \in V, \mathbf{r}' \in V \quad (4)$$

where G is the space-time Green's function for a space- and time-invariant medium (except for the delta modulation at $t = t_{ITM}$). The ITM acts as a source throughout the volume for all $\mathbf{r} \in V$ at t_{ITM} . Thus, the ITM can be seen as a new initial condition. In contrast, the classic TRM performs a time-reversal via TR-sources on the boundary $\mathbf{r} \in \partial V$ acting on all t , and thus imposes a boundary condition. The wave-field of the ITM reflection ϕ^{ITM_r} focuses at $t_A = t_{ITM} + (t_{ITM} - t_S)$, in the focal spot location $\mathbf{r}_0 = \mathbf{r}$, from where it then diverges for $t > t_A$. Hence, t_A acts as the source time state for the diverging waves. The resulting field is described by Eq. (5) and visualized in Fig. 2(c), where the star indicates the Dirac Delta source location at t_S, \mathbf{r}_0 , and circles indicate volumetric sources at t_{ITM}, \mathbf{r}' . Black circles indicate the "active" volumetric ITM sources, where the wavefront propagating away from t_S, \mathbf{r}_0 coincides with \mathbf{r}' at t_{ITM} , while gray circles indicate that the volumetric sources are inactive. The time reflection ϕ^{ITM_r} can thus also be expressed as follows:

$$\phi^{ITM}(t_B, \mathbf{r}) \propto \int_V G(t_B, \mathbf{r} | t_A, \mathbf{r}_0) G(t_A, \mathbf{r}_0 | t_{ITM}, \mathbf{r}') G(t_{ITM}, \mathbf{r}' | t_S, \mathbf{r}_0) d\mathbf{r}' \quad (5)$$

On the time arrow, t_S and t_A are mirror times of each other, with the mirror located at t_{ITM} . Considering time-reversal invariance and allowing acausal solutions, we can thus replace t_S by t_A in Eq. (4):

$$\phi^{ITM}(t_B, \mathbf{r}) \propto \int_V G(t_B, \mathbf{r} | t_{ITM}, \mathbf{r}') G(t_{ITM}, \mathbf{r}' | t_A, \mathbf{r}_0) d\mathbf{r}', \quad t_A = 2t_{ITM} - t_S, \quad \mathbf{r} \in V, \mathbf{r}' \in V \quad (6)$$

Hence, we have:

$$\phi^{ITM}(t_B, \mathbf{r}) \propto G(t_B, \mathbf{r} | t_A, \mathbf{r}_0), \quad t_A = 2t_{ITM} - t_S \quad (7)$$

which expresses that the field at t_B due to the ITM at t_{ITM} can be seen as the field due to a source in t_A . The focusing time t_A of the ITM is a virtual source time state for $t > t_{ITM}$. We now identify the time-reversed or focusing field for $t_{ITM} < t_B^- < t_A$ as the acausal (focusing or ingoing) solution and for $t_B^+ > t_A$ as the causal (outgoing) solution due to a virtual source at t_A, \mathbf{r}_0 :

$$\phi(t_B^-, \mathbf{r}) \propto G^{IN}(t_B^-, \mathbf{r} | t_A, \mathbf{r}_0), \quad t_B^- = t_A - \Delta t \quad (8)$$

$$\phi(t_B^+, \mathbf{r}) \propto G^{OUT}(t_B^+, \mathbf{r} | t_A, \mathbf{r}_0), \quad t_B^+ = t_A + \Delta t \quad (9)$$

Applying time-reversal invariance to the second G on the RHS of Eq. (6) we get:

$$\phi^{ITM_r}(t_B, \mathbf{r}) \propto \int_V G(t_B, \mathbf{r} | t_{ITM}, \mathbf{r}') G(t_A, \mathbf{r}_0 | t_{ITM}, \mathbf{r}') d\mathbf{r}', \quad t_A = 2t_{ITM} - t_S, \quad \mathbf{r} \in V, \mathbf{r}' \in V \quad (10)$$

Let us now investigate how Eq. (10), the ITM reflection field expressed by Green's functions, relates to cross-correlations in space.

The ITM reflection and spatial cross-correlation

For a spatially invariant medium, the wave-field at any time after the volumetric time reversal $t_B > t_{ITM} > t_S$ can be expressed through a temporal Green's function $G_t(t_B, t_A, \mathbf{r})$, which translates the field from time state t_A to another time state t_B over all \mathbf{r} . This temporal Green's function is expressed in the same way as Eq. (1), without specification of the source position of the variable of convolution (time in Eq. (1), space in Eq. (12)). Eq. (10) thus becomes:

$$\phi^{ITM_r}(t_B, \mathbf{r}) \propto \int_V G_t(t_B, t_{ITM}, \mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}') G_t(t_A, t_{ITM}, -\mathbf{r}') d\mathbf{r}', \quad \mathbf{r} \in V, \mathbf{r}' \in V \quad (11)$$

$$\phi^{ITM_r}(t_B, \mathbf{r}) \propto G_t(t_B, t_{ITM}, \mathbf{r}) *_r G_t(t_A, t_{ITM}, -\mathbf{r}), \quad (12)$$

G_t is the Green's function that maps all space states $\mathbf{r} \in V$ to all $\mathbf{r} \in V$ from one time to another for a space-invariant medium, analogue to G_r , which maps one space state to another over all times t for a time-invariant medium. Because it describes the mapping from one time state to another for all space states inside the volume integral, it cannot differentiate individual space states. This is orthogonal to the usually considered Green's function G_r which maps the field from one space state to another, and acts over all t in the considered time-integral. The wave backtraces its path with respect to the virtual source position t_A , hence the $-\mathbf{r}$ on the RHS. This result from time-reversal invariance, is most intuitively understood via its counterpart in the wavenumber domain. Let us therefore define the n-dimensional spatial Fourier transform for the wavenumber domain:

$$\check{F}(\mathbf{k}, t) = \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} f(\mathbf{r}, t) e^{-i\mathbf{k}\cdot\mathbf{r}} d^n\mathbf{r} \quad (13)$$

In the spatial Fourier domain, Eq. (12) becomes:

$$\check{\phi}^{ITM_r}(t_B, \mathbf{k}) \propto \check{G}_t(t_B, t_{ITM}, \mathbf{k}) \check{G}_t^*(t_A, t_{ITM}, \mathbf{k}) \quad (14)$$

$$(15)$$

Because the ITM is modeled as an infinitesimally short delta-like perturbation—or, in practical experiments ([32]), as a square pulse whose temporal width is smaller than the wave period—the medium can be treated as effectively lossless. By invoking Hermitian symmetry, Eq. (14) can then be rewritten as:

$$\check{\phi}^{ITM_r}(t_B, \mathbf{k}) \propto \check{G}_t(t_B, t_{ITM}, \mathbf{k}) \check{G}_t(t_A, t_{ITM}, -\mathbf{k}) \quad (16)$$

$$(17)$$

Hence, the acausal solution is a backpropagating wave that focuses in t_A, \mathbf{r}_0 . For a spatially invariant medium, Eq. (9) can thus be expressed through in- and out-going temporal Green's function \check{G}_t and G_t :

$$\check{\phi}^{ITM_r}(t_B^-, \mathbf{k}) \propto \check{G}^{t_{IN}}(t_B^-, t_A, -\mathbf{k}) \quad (18) \quad \phi^{ITM_r}(t_B^-, \mathbf{r}) \propto G^{t_{IN}}(t_B^-, t_A, -\mathbf{r}) \quad (20)$$

$$\check{\phi}^{ITM_r}(t_B^+, \mathbf{k}) \propto \check{G}^{t_{OUT}}(t_B^+, t_A, \mathbf{k}) \quad (19) \quad \phi^{ITM_r}(t_B^+, \mathbf{r}) \propto G^{t_{OUT}}(t_B^+, t_A, \mathbf{r}) \quad (21)$$

The ingoing (acausal) $G_t(t_B^-, t_A, -\mathbf{r})$ and outgoing (causal) $G_t(t_B^+, t_A, \mathbf{r})$ are indistinguishable, since both functions are mirror images of each other and the time-dependency of G

(a) Volumetric control: spatial focusing from V (b) Temporal control - spatial focusing from ∂V (c) Temporal control - no focusing from ∂V

Figure 3: ITM - TRM comparison (a) The Instantaneous-Time-Mirror can reverse any wave-field existing in V at any time through volumetric wave-field control. (b) Boundary TR sources are excited at different times due to different arrival times (Last In - First Out). The ITM achieves the same result instantaneously through volumetric control, see (a) and Fig. 2 c). (c) Contrary to the ITM, the TRM cannot reverse the wave-field prior to its arrival at the boundary ∂V .

and G_r is lost. Only when evaluating G_t for several time-states or by including the time derivative $\frac{\partial G_t}{\partial t}$, the propagation direction is resolved and the causal and acausal Green's function can be distinguished.

In contrast, for correlations in time as in Eq. (3) one retrieves the causal ($G_r(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}_A, t)$) and acausal ($G_r(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}_A, -t)$) Green's functions of a temporally invariant medium, where the propagation direction is resolved through time-dependency. A comparison of Eq. (8) and Eq. (12) shows the following: the correlation over \mathbf{r} of the wave-fields observed at t_B and t_A , due to the impulsive and volumetric sources of an Instantaneous Time Mirror at t_{ITM} acting on a delta pulse at t_S , where $t_S = t_A - 2t_{ITM}$, results in the temporal Green's function G_t due to a delta source at time state t_A . If $t_B < t_A$, it gives the acausal temporal Green's function, and if $t_B > t_A$ it gives the causal temporal Green's function. For $t_B = t_A$ we get the focusing field equivalent to a source or sink in t_A , and thus the superposition of the causal and acausal Green's function.

So far we have investigated the equivalence of an ITM with cross-correlation in space for a single spatio-temporal Dirac Delta source. Let us now investigate the case of spatially diffuse wave-fields.

Spatial Green's function retrieval in diffuse wave-fields: temporally coherent sources

In order to compare Eq. (12) to interferometry in the space-domain, let us examine the cross-correlation CC^{t_A, t_B} of the volumetric wave-field at two time states t_A and t_B due to randomly distributed sources in $\mathbf{r} \in V$, excited at t_e , where $t_e < t_B$ and $t_e < t_A$. Let us consider the ideal case, where the sources are all excited simultaneously with a Dirac delta:

$$N(\mathbf{r}, t) = \sum_i \delta(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}_i, t - t_e), \quad (22)$$

The wave field at t_A and t_B due to these sources is then described by:

$$\phi(\mathbf{r}, t_A) = \sum_i G(t_A, t_e, \mathbf{r}) \delta(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}_i, t - t_e) = G(t_A, t_e, \mathbf{r}) N(\mathbf{r}, t) \quad (23)$$

$$\phi(\mathbf{r}, t_B) = \sum_i G(t_B, t_e, \mathbf{r}) \delta(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}_i, t - t_e) = G(t_B, t_e, \mathbf{r}) N(\mathbf{r}, t) \quad (24)$$

and the spatial cross-correlation of those two wave-fields is:

$$CC(t_A, t_B, \Delta \mathbf{r}) = \int_V \phi(\mathbf{r}, t_A) \phi(\mathbf{r} + \Delta \mathbf{r}, t_B) d\mathbf{r} \quad (25)$$

$$CC(t_A, t_B, \Delta \mathbf{r}) = \int_V \phi(\mathbf{r} - \Delta \mathbf{r}, t_A) \phi(\mathbf{r}, t_B) d\mathbf{r} \quad (26)$$

Hence, we have:

$$CC^{t_A, t_B}(\mathbf{r}) \propto \int_V [G(t_A, t_e, \mathbf{r}) N(t_A, \mathbf{r})] [G(t_B, t_e, \mathbf{r}) N(t_B, \mathbf{r} + \Delta \mathbf{r})] d\mathbf{r} \quad (27)$$

$$CC^{t_A, t_B}(\mathbf{r}) \propto \int_V [G(t_A, t_e, \mathbf{r}) N(t_A, \mathbf{r} - \Delta \mathbf{r})] [G(t_B, t_e, \mathbf{r}) N(t_B, \mathbf{r})] d\mathbf{r} \quad (28)$$

and in the spatial frequency domain:

$$\check{C}C^{t_A, t_B}(\mathbf{k}) \propto [\check{G}^*(t_B, t_e, \mathbf{k}) \check{N}^*(t_B, \mathbf{k})] [G(t_A, t_e, \mathbf{k}) \check{N}(t_A, \mathbf{k})] \quad (29)$$

Assuming that our field is real valued, due to Hermitian symmetry, we have:

$$\check{C}C^{t_A, t_B}(\mathbf{k}) \propto [\check{G}(t_A, t_e, -\mathbf{k}) \check{N}(t_A, -\mathbf{k})] [G(t_B, t_e, \mathbf{k}) \check{N}(t_B, \mathbf{k})] \quad (30)$$

Because the Dirac sources are randomly distributed throughout the domain, the sum of Eq. (22) becomes an integral:

$$N(\mathbf{r}, t) = \int_V \delta(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}', t - t_e) d\mathbf{r}', \quad (31)$$

$$\check{N}(\mathbf{k}, t) = \delta(\mathbf{k}, t - t_e), \quad (32)$$

Therefore, above equation can be written as

$$\check{C}C^{t_A, t_B}(\mathbf{k}) \propto \check{G}(t_A, t_e, -\mathbf{k}) G(t_B, t_e, \mathbf{k}) \quad (33)$$

and going back to the \mathbf{r} -domain:

$$CC^{t_A, t_B}(\mathbf{r}) \propto \int_V G_t(t_B, t_e, \mathbf{r}) G_t(t_A, t_e, -\mathbf{r}) d\mathbf{r} \quad (34)$$

Both, t_e in Eq. (34) and t_{ITM} in Eq. (12) both consist of volumetric delta sources, thus we can directly compare Eq. (12) to Eq. (34). Setting $t_e = t_{ITM}$ we see that the RHS of Eq. (34) and Eq. (12) are equal, and hence:

$$CC^{t_A, t_B}(\mathbf{r}) \propto G^{t_{OUT}}(t_B, t_A, \mathbf{r}), t_B > t_A \quad (35)$$

$$CC^{t_A, t_B}(\mathbf{r}) \propto G^{t_{IN}}(t_B, t_A, -\mathbf{r}), t_B < t_A \quad (36)$$

For a spatially homogeneous medium, $G_t(t_A, t_e, -\mathbf{r}) = G_t(t_A, t_e, \mathbf{r})$, and as a consequence the relation still holds when choosing $t_B < t_A$ [45].

Thus, the cross-correlation of the spatial signals of a spatially homogeneous medium at two time states t_A and t_B due to impulsive sources everywhere in $\mathbf{r} \in V$ at $t_e < t_A, t_B$ leads to the retrieval of the acausal, converging temporal Green's function $G_t(t_B^-, t_A, -\mathbf{r})$ or causal diverging temporal Green's function $G_t(t_B^+, t_A, \mathbf{r})$ in t_B for a source at t_A, \mathbf{r}_0 . Hence, the spatial cross-correlation field is equivalent to a volumetric time-reversal field of the ITM type:

$$CC^{t_A, t_B}(\mathbf{r}) \equiv \phi_{t_A, t_B}^{ITM}(\mathbf{r})$$

Depending on the t_B chosen, either the acausal or causal solution is computed. The causality of the recovered Green's function depends on the choice of t_A and t_B . if $t_A < t_B$ the causal Green's function is recovered and reversing this choice, which can be seen as a time-reversal, yields the acausal Green's function. Therefore, sources are only needed on one side of the time-arrow. Eqs. (12) and (34) are therefore one-sided representations, similar to the theorems derived by [31]. It is noteworthy that a different type of one-sided theorems have been derived by [46] for time-lapse monitoring with a scattering operator in the temporal frequency domain. In contrast to our present case and [31], classic noise correlation and the boundary controlled time-reversal mirror are based on two-sided theorems, which yield both the causal and acausal Green's function.

Correlation in space and correlation in time of a diffuse wave-field due to coherent delta sources are schematically illustrated in Fig. 2(b) and (d). Fig. 2(a) and c), and Fig. 3 show the resulting time-reversal fields and illustrate the main difference between the ITM and the TRM: The ITM controls the temporal focusing through spatial control. The TRM controls the spatial focusing through temporal control [47].

The ITM transmission

So far we have shown that the correlation in space of two time states t_A, t_B , due to randomly distributed impulsive sources, all firing at time t_{ITM} , is proportional to the wave-field at t_B due to an instantaneous time mirror acting at t_{ITM} on a wave-field created by a single impulsive source at t_S , where $t_{ITM} - t_S = t_A - t_{ITM}$. However, we have only discussed the time reflection of the ITM. In boundary time-reversal (TRM) the reflection alone describes the entire wave-field since it is captured, reversed and re-emitted from the boundary. In contrast to the TRM, a realistic ITM [25] will always create a time transmission in addition to a time reflection. In the following, we will show that the time transmission is also recovered for spatial cross-correlation of spatially diffuse wave-fields due to temporally

coherent sources. Following [48], section 8b) the solution to this Green's function is:

$$\check{G}_t(\mathbf{k}, t_A, t_{ITM}) = \frac{\sin(|k|c(t_A - t_{ITM}))}{\beta c|k|}, \quad (37)$$

where β is mass density in the acoustic and inverse shear modulus in the elastic case. Note that this sin-function is different from the complex exponential functions that we are used to when analysing G_r in the $x - \omega$ -domain. Under our previous assumptions to ignore time-derivatives, assume time- and space-invariant media, and consider real-valued wave-fields, we get:

$$\check{G}_t(\mathbf{k}, t_A, t_{ITM}) \approx \cos(|k|c(t_A - t_{ITM})), \quad (38)$$

Hence, by substituting $a = |k|c(t_A - t_{ITM})$ and $b = |k|c(t_B - t_{ITM})$, we obtain for the cross-correlation on the RHS of Eq. (16) (or Eq. (33) with variable substitution):

$$\cos(a)\cos(b) = \frac{1}{2}\cos(a - b) + \frac{1}{2}\cos(a + b) \quad (39)$$

$$= \frac{1}{2}\cos(|k|c(t_A - t_B)) + \frac{1}{2}\cos(|k|c(t_A + t_B - 2t_{ITM})) \quad (40)$$

$$= \frac{1}{2}\cos(|k|c(t_A - t_B)) + \frac{1}{2}\cos(|k|c(t_B)) \quad (41)$$

Since both functions are real-valued, we can skip the complex conjugation sign that is usually associated to correlations. Here the term $\cos(a - b)$ is, apart from a phase-shift $\frac{\pi}{2}$ and a factor $\frac{1}{2|k|}$, a Green's function for the time difference $t_A - t_B$. Thus, for $t_B = t_A + \Delta t$ we recover the causal, and for $t_B = t_A - \Delta t$ we recover the acausal solution due to a time mirror at t_{ITM} and a delta source at t_S . In our ITM-equivalence it corresponds to the time reflected field. In contrast, the term $\cos(a + b)$ corresponds to the Green's function for a sum of two times. How does this solution to the correlation of the two wave-fields correspond to our ITM-equivalence? In fact, it turns out that the sum of the two times is $\cos(a + b) = \cos(|k|c(t_A + t_B - 2t_{ITM}))$. Thus, since in our thought experiment we define $t_A = 2t_{ITM} + t_S$, where t_S is the source time of the impulse in time and space, this term corresponds to the Green's function for a time t_B due to a delta source at t_S and we can write Eq. (41) as:

$$\cos(a)\cos(b) = \frac{1}{2}\cos(|k|c(t_A - t_B)) + \frac{1}{2}\cos(|k|c(t_S + t_B)), \quad (42)$$

This sum of two times equals the time t_B , and is always causal as long as $t_B > t_{ITM}$, which we have previously defined. In our time mirror equivalence, the resulting wavefront corresponds to the time transmission that accompanies the time reflection of the time mirror at t_{ITM} . Indeed, for any experimental instantaneous time mirror, such as Losschmidt freezing, or decoupling of the wave-field and its time derivative, a transmission will be physically present. While in boundary time reversal the entire wave can be played back, the transmission coefficient of an instantaneous time mirror can not be smaller 0.5, and the reflection coefficient cannot exceed 0.5 [43]. What happens to this equivalence to the ITM transmission in the case of correlation in space of a wave-field due to incoherent noise sources?

Spatial Green's function retrieval in diffuse wave-fields: temporally incoherent noise sources

Let us therefore investigate the more general model with noise of the form $\check{N}(\mathbf{k}, t)$, where

$$\left\langle \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} N(\mathbf{x}, t) N(\mathbf{x}' + \mathbf{x}, t') d^n \mathbf{x} \right\rangle = \delta(t - t') S(\mathbf{x}', t), \quad (43)$$

$$\langle \check{N}^*(\mathbf{k}, t) \check{N}(\mathbf{k}, t') \rangle = \delta(t - t') \check{S}(\mathbf{k}, t). \quad (44)$$

Hence, we allow non-impulsive noise sources, where $\check{S}(\mathbf{k}, t) \neq 1$, relax the temporal coherency requirement of the sources, and excite the sources at different times t' . With this noise model, we define

$$\check{p}(\mathbf{k}, t_A) = \frac{1}{\alpha(t_A)} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \check{G}_t(\mathbf{k}, t_A, t) \check{N}(\mathbf{k}, t) dt, \quad (45)$$

$$\check{p}(\mathbf{k}, t_B) = \frac{1}{\alpha(t_B)} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \check{G}_t(\mathbf{k}, t_B, t') \check{N}(\mathbf{k}, t') dt', \quad (46)$$

where the noise \check{N} acts as the source function that is propagated by \check{G}_t to give the field $\check{p}(\mathbf{k}, t_A)$ and $\check{p}(\mathbf{k}, t_B)$. Here, α is the time dependent medium property, which in the acoustic case would be the bulk modulus. Hence, the cross-correlation of the time states t_A and t_B , expressed in the spatial Fourier domain as an ensemble average $\langle \dots \rangle$ gives:

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \check{p}^*(\mathbf{k}, t_A) \check{p}(\mathbf{k}, t_B) \rangle &= \frac{1}{\alpha(t_A) \alpha(t_B)} \left\langle \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \check{G}_t^*(\mathbf{k}, t_A, t) \check{G}_t(\mathbf{k}, t_B, t') \check{N}^*(\mathbf{k}, t) \check{N}(\mathbf{k}, t') \right\rangle dt' dt \\ &= \frac{1}{\alpha(t_A) \alpha(t_B)} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \check{G}_t^*(\mathbf{k}, t_A, t) \check{G}_t(\mathbf{k}, t_B, t) \check{S}(\mathbf{k}, t) dt. \end{aligned} \quad (47)$$

Using the same assumption as previously, we now analyse this for the special case of a time-independent medium. Analogously to equation Eq. (41) we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \check{p}^*(\mathbf{k}, t_A) \check{p}(\mathbf{k}, t_B) \rangle &= \frac{1}{2\alpha^2} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \left[\cos(|\mathbf{k}|c(t_B - t_A)) + \cos(|\mathbf{k}|c(t_B + t_A - 2t)) \right] \check{S}(\mathbf{k}, t) dt \\ &= \frac{\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \check{S}(\mathbf{k}, t) dt}{2\alpha^2} \left(\check{G}_t^{OUT}(\mathbf{k}, t_B, t_A) - \{ \check{G}_t^{IN}(\mathbf{k}, t_B, t_A) \}^* \right) \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{2\alpha^2} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \left[\cos(|\mathbf{k}|c(t_B + t_A - 2t)) \right] \check{S}(\mathbf{k}, t) dt. \end{aligned} \quad (48)$$

(49)

The integration of the incoherent terms $\cos(|\mathbf{k}|c(t_B + t_A - 2t)) \check{S}(\mathbf{k}, t)$ gives a significantly smaller contribution than the integration of the coherent terms $\cos(|\mathbf{k}|c(t_B - t_A)) \check{S}(\mathbf{k}, t)$. Therefore, recovery of the ITM reflection and thus Eq. (36) is also confirmed for cross-correlation in space of temporally non-coherent noise sources and a time-independent medium. However, the ITM transmission of temporally uncorrelated noise sources is not coherent, and, contrary to temporally correlated noise sources, cross-correlation in space of such a diffuse wave-field does not recover the transmission of a single Dirac Delta. To what extent Eq. (36) holds for heterogeneous, time-dependent media will be investigated in a different publication focusing on Green's function retrieval in varying media (see [39]). In the present manuscript, we complete the theoretical part by investigating the remaining link in 1: How does the Green's function retrieval we derived so far relate to the SPAC-method employed by the seismological community?

Consistency of the ITM - cross correlation equivalence with SPAC

[28] already have shown that time domain noise correlation is consistent with SPAC (spatial autocorrelation), which for practical reasons is often calculated in the temporal frequency domain. It therefore stands to reason to compare our formulation for spatial cross-correlation of discrete time steps to SPAC. We thus compare our solution of the spatial cross-correlation in Eq. (41) to the SPAC solution as given by [28]. As stated in the introduction SPAC uses time integrals as a proxy for ensemble averaging [28]. Thus, the original formulation by Aki, where u is displacement in the elastic case:

$$\phi(\xi, t) \equiv \frac{1}{A} \int_A u(\mathbf{r}, t) u(\mathbf{r} + \xi, t) d\mathbf{r}$$

becomes for a time-independent $\phi(\xi, t)$:

$$\phi(\xi) \equiv \frac{1}{2T} \int_{-T}^T u(\mathbf{r}, t) u(\mathbf{r} + \xi, t) dt$$

and the solution in the temporal frequency domain is [28]:

$$\phi(\xi, \omega) = \frac{1}{2T} \int_{-T}^T \cos[\omega(t - t_1)] \cos[\omega(t - t_2)] dt \quad (50)$$

$$= \frac{1}{2} \cos(\omega(t_2 - t_1)) + \frac{\sin(2\omega T)}{4\omega T} \cos[\omega(t_1 + t_2)], \quad (51)$$

where θ is azimuth, \mathbf{x} and ξ are spatial variables, and A is an area. With $c = \frac{\omega}{k}$, we see the close similarity of Eq. (51) with Eq. (41). Letting $T \rightarrow 0$ we recover:

$$\phi(\xi, \omega) = \frac{1}{2} \cos(\mathbf{k}c(t_2 - t_1)) + \frac{1}{2} \cos[\mathbf{k}c(t_1 + t_2)], \quad (52)$$

In Eq. (41) we re-substitute t_S for t_{ITM} in a and b and set $t_S = 0$:

$$\cos(a)\cos(b) = \frac{1}{2}\cos(|\mathbf{k}|c(t_A - t_B)) + \frac{1}{2}\cos(|\mathbf{k}|c(t_A + t_B)) \quad (53)$$

Eq. (52) and Eq. (53) are exactly equivalent. Thus, in the limit of $T \rightarrow 0$, SPAC is also equivalent to our ITM interpretation, with the first term representing the time reflection and the second term representing the time transmission. As noted by [28], the cross-terms, representing the sum of two times, get cancelled in the case of uncorrelated noise sources for the SPAC averaging. This is exactly what we found in the previous section and signifies that the transmission of the ITM is not recovered for the cross-correlation in space of a diffuse wave-field due to uncorrelated noise sources. Having established the theory, we show in the next section numerically the ITM equivalence and how spatial correlation of scarce time samples allows focal spot monitoring.

INSTANTANEOUS MONITORING WITH THE ITM - NUMERICAL EXPERIMENT

In ambient noise interferometry and related methods, the temporal degrees of freedom of broadband signals allow for recovering medium properties between individual sensors. These

cross-correlations of temporal signals at different sensors are particularly suited for imaging of time invariant media. In contrast, if one wants to monitor rather than image the medium, the temporal windows needed for the cross-correlations might include the medium-changes one tries to recover. In the ideal case, monitoring would avoid time-windows altogether to recover medium changes in real-time. With the advent of dense array acquisitions, previously untapped spatial degrees of freedom of wave-fields are now accessible in data acquisition. As a consequence, the temporal windows needed for interferometric monitoring could be largely reduced, as we have shown in the previous section on [Volumetric time-reversal](#), where two time-steps are sufficient for Green’s function retrieval. Currently, the dense array imaging methods with the highest spatial resolution for acoustic and elastic waves can probably be found in medical imaging: Shear wave imaging is a routinely applied dense array imaging method where the pixels of an ultrasonic or magnetic resonance image are turned into single-component particle velocity sensors. Thus, the particle velocities of an elastic wave-field in soft tissues, like the human body, can be measured through speckle tracking. Equivalently, in optics, particle imaging velocimetry and optical coherence tomography can retrieve particle velocities of an elastic surface wave field observed by a camera. While the cross-correlation we derived in [Volumetric time-reversal](#) holds for any type of acoustic or elastic wave (see representation theorems in [43, 48]), in the following we consider the case of shear waves in soft tissue for two reasons:

1. Elastography in soft tissues is a well established method which is routinely applied in hospitals and allows for an unparalleled spatial resolution of the elastic wave field.
2. The order of magnitude contrast of compression ($\approx 1500\text{m/s}$) and shear waves ($< 10\text{ m/s}$) in soft tissues allows us to focus on the shear wave-field, since P- and S-wave are naturally separating in time. This greatly simplifies analysis, interpretation, and visualization of the results.

We think that the relevance of dense arrays in elastic wave field sensing is currently much larger than in acoustics, which motivates our choice to showcase an elastic numerical example. In addition to elastography, very dense arrays are encountered in seismic node studies and distributed acoustic sensing (DAS) with fibre optics (which employs elastic waves). These studies are becoming more and more common in Non-Destructive-Testing (NDT), environmental seismology, and seismic surveys for imaging and monitoring [49–54].

Simulation setup

We start with a spatially diffuse wave-field, where all polarizations and angles of propagation are present. Such a field can be achieved through scattering or homogeneously distributed sources. Our field results from multiple spatially distributed dipolar noise sources. Each source is represented by a force vector with randomly oriented directionality. To generate a broadband wavefield, we prescribe an initial condition in a two-dimensional elastic spectral-element simulation performed with the SALVUS software package [55]. As [56] point out, simultaneous emission of a Dirac delta impulse of many sources is equivalent to an accumulation of noise sources over time for time-domain noise interferometry. In our configuration, the Initial conditions replaces the Dirac delta at initial source activation time $t_e = t_{\text{ITM}}$. For the resulting wave-field, in a spatially and temporally homogenous medium, the correlation of two time states in space will give the same time-averaged correlation function as correlation in time of two receivers. We set the compression wave speed of the medium to $1500\frac{\text{m}}{\text{s}}$ and the shear wave speed to $2\frac{\text{m}}{\text{s}}$. The particle velocity is calculated by

Figure 4: Temporal evolution of a spatially diffuse wave-field due to impulsive sources of random amplitude, directionality, and distribution inside the Region-Of-Interest. Single component particle velocity snapshots of a 2D elastic spectral element simulation are shown. The employed elastic and acoustic wave-speeds mimic soft tissue encountered for example in muscles or organs. The first snapshot is dominated by the elastic near-field or coupling term, which attenuates quickly with distance. The remaining snapshots are dominated by the shear wave far-field.

sampling the simulated displacement wave-field at $4000Hz$, a realistic sampling frequency in elastography, and differentiating it in time. A central Region-of-Interest of the vertical component of the particle velocity for 30000 sources distributed over $5x5cm^2$ is depicted in Fig. 4[45].

The first snapshot in Fig. 4 is lacking the smaller wavelengths the other snapshots exhibit. The clear difference in wavelength of the observed field between the first and consequent snapshots is due to the dominance of the elastic near field or coupling field [57–59], sometimes also called dilatational lobe in the first panel, which subsequently attenuates very quickly. The shear wave which is dominating the other snapshots has not yet propagated far from the sources at $t = 0.25ms$. For all time states, all angles of propagation are present. However, because the receivers are single component, the measured particle velocity $\frac{\partial u_x}{\partial t}$ is blind to purely y -polarized waves ($k_x = 0$).

Numerical ITM via cross-correlation

Following the derivation in section Volumetric time-reversal and Eq. (22) to Eq. (34), the cross-correlation in space between two time states of the diffuse wave-field gives a time-reversal field of the ITM type. This ITM-field is described in concise notation for the numerical simulation by Eq. (54):

$$\phi_{t_A,t}^{ITM}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{t}) = \frac{\partial u_x}{\partial t}(\mathbf{r}, t) *_r \frac{\partial u_x}{\partial t}(-\mathbf{r}, t_A), \quad \mathbf{r}' \in V, \mathbf{r} \in V \quad (54)$$

where u_x is particle displacement in x . Fig. 5 shows the result of the cross-correlation for setting $t_A = 2ms$, and correlating it with different time states $t_B \in t$. Both, time state t_B , and the correlation time difference $t_B - t_A$ are indicated to illustrate the time-symmetries and focusing time. The top row of Fig. 5 shows snapshots of cross-correlations in space between a time state t_A and $t_A - 1.25ms, t_A - 0.75ms, t_A, t_A + 0.75ms, t_A + 1.25ms$. The bottom row shows the corresponding space-series extracted along x at $y = 0$. The wavefronts appearing in the correlation are mirror-symmetric: for negative correlation times, a circular

wavefront collapses towards the centre, for positive correlation times it diverges from the centre. Furthermore, a second wavefront of larger radius diverges for all times. The two wavefronts can be interpreted as the reflection and transmission of an ITM at excitation time $t_e = t_{ITM}$, which we expect from the derivation in [Volumetric time-reversal](#). From any two correlation snapshots, we can thus calculate the time-of-flight of the appearing wavefront. The resulting wave speed is indicated in Fig. 6. It is within 10% of the true wave-speed of $2 \frac{m}{s}$, which is within the error defined by the space and time discretizations of the observation. Hence, by evaluating two cross-correlations between different time states of our space- and time-invariant medium, we recover the causal (outgoing) and acausal (ingoing) Green's function. In contrast to correlations in time, we recover the transfer function between two time states t_A and t_B , instead of the spatial Green's function between two receiver positions. As long as the two time states are separated by at least half a period, which is the temporal diffraction limit that follows from the time-frequency uncertainty relation, the medium's wave speed can thus be retrieved. The assumption of temporal invariance is required over the interval separating the two evaluated time steps. In many monitoring applications, the sampling interval is substantially shorter than the characteristic time scale associated with changes in the medium, and this assumption is therefore justified. Consequently, by continuously computing cross-correlations between successive time states, variations in the medium properties can be monitored in a quasi-instantaneous manner. In the case of temporally correlated noise sources, the ITM transmission and source activation time can be recovered, as indicated in Fig. 7. Although most interferometry applications consider temporally uncorrelated noise sources, recent developments suggest possible applications for interferometry with correlated noise sources [34, 60].

Figure 5: Field recovered from the correlation in space between different time states of the diffuse wave-field in Fig. 4. The third panel results from autocorrelation in space, the correlation of one time state with itself. The same snapshot is correlated with preceding and consequent snapshots for the remaining panels, giving the ingoing Green's function for correlation with earlier snapshots (negative times), and the outgoing Green's function for correlation with for correlation with later snapshots (positive times). The bottom row is the 1D extract in x at the center y -location of the top row.

Focal spot imaging and instantaneous monitoring

For $t_A = t_B$, Eq. (54) describes an autocorrelation in space and results in the focal spot we can observe in the third panel (t_0) of Fig. 5. A commonly used measure is the Full-Width-Half-Maximum of the spot, where $FWHM \approx \frac{\lambda}{2}$ [61]. For example, in Fig. 5 and Fig. 6, panels 3, we retrieve an FWHM of $0.4mm$ in x and $0.8mm$ in y . For the same simulation parameters, only now, setting the shear wave speed to $1\frac{m}{s}$ instead of $2\frac{m}{s}$, we retrieve an FMHW of $0.3mm$ in x and $0.5mm$ in y . The elongation of the focal spot orthogonal to the observation polarity is well-known: Waves that propagate along x contribute more to the time-reversal focusing because our polarised sensors have no sensitivity in y . The focal spots from the correlation in space strongly resemble the focal spots retrieved for the zero-lag cross-correlation of time-series between all receivers of a dense array in a diffuse wave field [11, 62]. Those have previously been shown to be a time-domain interferometry equivalent to SPAC [11, 28–30, 35]. They have been used for medical imaging [11] [63–65], seismology [62, 66, 67], and non-destructive testing [68] to resolve medium inhomogeneities in space. By extending Eq. (1) to all spatial positions \mathbf{r} , the temporal cross-correlation between a given receiver and the entire receiver array of the diffuse fields in Fig. 4 yields the time-reversed field $\phi_{\mathbf{r}_0, \mathbf{r}}^{TR}(\mathbf{r}, t)$:

$$\phi_{\mathbf{r}_0, \mathbf{r}}^{TR}(\mathbf{r}, t) \propto \frac{\partial u_x}{\partial t}(\mathbf{r}_0, -t) *_t \frac{\partial u_x}{\partial t}(\mathbf{r}, t), \quad \mathbf{r} \in V, \quad \phi_{\mathbf{r}_0, \mathbf{r}}^{TR} \equiv CC^{\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}_0}(t) \quad (55)$$

It is plotted in Fig. 7. In comparison with Fig. 5 and Fig. 6 we can barely identify the focusing and diverging TR-field. The zero-lag cross-correlation focal spot retrieved for $\tau = 0$ and shown in panel 3 is embedded in a much noisier background than its spatial equivalent in Fig. 5 and Fig. 6. This can be explained by information theory: For the autocorrelation in space only one time state is sampled, and consequently, due to the time-frequency uncertainty relation $\Delta f \Delta t \geq \frac{1}{2\pi}$ [69] chapter 2, [70], all information on f is lost. However, the space-wavenumber uncertainty relation, $\Delta k \Delta r \geq \frac{1}{2}$, is fulfilled for a broad band in \mathbf{k} . In our numerical example, this means that the zero-lag autocorrelation in time is limited by $\Delta t = 0.25ms$, while the autocorrelation in space is limited by $\Delta y = 0.33mm$ and $\Delta x = 0.04mm$. Hence, solving \mathbf{k} for wavelength λ we get: $\lambda_{y_{min}} = 2\Delta y = 0.66mm$ and $\lambda_{x_{min}} = 2\Delta x = 0.08mm$. The corresponding frequencies for a linear elastic medium with wavespeed $c = 2\frac{m}{s}$ are $f_{max1} = \frac{c}{\lambda_{x_{min}}} = 23.9kHz$ and $f_{max2} = \frac{c}{\lambda_{y_{min}}} = 2.99kHz$. In contrast, the time-sampling results in $f_{max} = \frac{1}{2\Delta t} = 2kHz$. Furthermore, the time-series for this experiment is only 100 samples long, while the space-series contains $(n_x \cdot n_y)$ samples. Thus, order of magnitude more space states enter into the spatial auto-correlation CC^{t_A, t_A} , then into the zero lag time cross-correlation. Hence, a broad spatial spectrum sampled at super-resolution (several points per shear-wavelength [71]) allows for the well resolved focusing in the autocorrelation of a single time state. The information content (degrees of freedom) accessed by the spatial correlation is larger than in the temporal correlation. As derived in [Volumetric time-reversal](#), the experimental analogue is an instantaneous time mirror (ITM), in which volumetric control exerted over a single temporal state (Loschmidt freezing) gives rise to time-reversal (TR) focusing. By contrast, the zero-lag temporal autocorrelation, although it operates between one receiver and all other receivers in the array, can only reverse those frequency components that are sampled at the temporal Nyquist frequency, rendering it formally equivalent to conventional (boundary/surface) time-reversal mirrors.

The focal spot reconstruction resulting from correlations over time can be performed for

Figure 6: Similar to Fig. 5, employing different time states (snapshots) of the field in Fig. 4 for the correlation. The time mirror interpretation of time transmission and time reflection recovered from the cross-correlation are indicated in the first panel of the bottom row. The measures indicated in panel 3,4,5 of the bottom row show how wave-speed c and source time $t_e = t_{ITM}$ can be calculated from the distance measures of the wavefronts (indicated by horizontal black lines) of the time reflection (panel 5) and time transmission (panel 3 and 4), and the time differences of the snapshots.

any pair of receiver positions and can resolve inhomogeneities in space but not in time. In contrast, the space-focal spot shown in Fig. 5 does not include any time integration. Although it can give no information on spatially localised properties, it allows retrieving temporal inhomogeneities. For unknown source spectra, the wavelengths could be monitored instantly, and for known spectra, the wave speed could be monitored instantly via the FWHM of the focal spot.

In practice, the autocorrelation of diffuse wave-fields is already used by several authors in shear wave elastography imaging. Therefore, small regions of interest are assumed to be spatially and/or temporally homogeneous and to enter the autocorrelation. In seismology, the consistency of time-reversal/noise correlation and spatial autocorrelation is well established by the earlier cited papers. By deriving the equivalence of ITM, Cross Correlation, and SPAC, the present numerical comparison also confirms that the zero-lag time of correlation in passive elastography [11, 34, 64, 71] and the autocorrelation in reverberant elastography [72, 73] are fundamentally connected through time-reversal physics [47].

CONCLUSION

We showed the equivalence of Green's function retrieval via diffuse wave-field correlations in space with the Instantaneous Time reversal Mirror (ITM). This establishes a missing link in the analogy of time-reversal physics and Green's function retrieval through wave-field correlation, which is put into context in Fig. 1. The analogy is illustrated through schematic illustrations and a numerical experiment, which confirms that cross-correlations in space can retrieve the temporal Green's function G_t between two time states for homogeneous media. Furthermore, our numerical experiment mimics a potential application: Near-Instantaneous medium property monitoring. In comparison with ambient noise interferometry, this result

Figure 7: Correlation in time between the central space state (\mathbf{r}_A) and all other space states of the diffuse wave-field in Fig. 4 ($\phi^{CC^t}(\mathbf{r}_B, t) = \sum_{\mathbf{r}_B \in V} \phi(\mathbf{r}_A, t) *_t \phi(\mathbf{r}_B, -t)$). The panel at 0 ms (t_{foc}) represents the zero lag cross-correlation or focal spot. t_{corr} indicates the shown lag of the correlation in time.

is achieved by leveraging the spatial information contained in the spatially diffuse wave-field instead of the temporal information. Our theoretical proof and numerical experiment hold for time-invariant media. Since variations in medium properties typically occur on time scales that are long relative to the temporal sampling rates achievable with acoustic and elastic waves, the proposed methodology remains directly relevant for monitoring applications. The extension of the theory to time-varying media is examined in [39]. In practice, algorithms that leverage time and space information simultaneously are currently more likely to be used for real-world monitoring applications [34]. Nevertheless, our work lays a theoretical foundation and experimentally illustrates the potential of dense arrays for instantaneous monitoring of medium properties.

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- which was emitted in B on the enclosing boundary. This will lead to focusing of the time-reversed field in A and consequent divergence from A. At B the acausal field, which exists at times before time-reversal focusing, and causal field, which exists at times after time-reversal focusing, are measured. Hence, cross-correlation of the time-series between positions (space states) A and B due to sources completely surrounding the medium leads to recovering of the field in B as if A was a source. This analogy is visually sketched in the top row of Fig. 2.
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